

Bleeding Profile as a Prognostic Indicator in Hepatotoxic Rodenticide Poisoning: A Cross-Sectional Study**Dhawanth Rathod¹, Shradhdha Jasoliya², Kishor Kalasariya³, Hiren Rathod⁴, Mohmad Sejarali Sayeed⁵, Sajidali S. Saiyad⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, Government Medical College, Surat²3rd Year Resident, Department of General Medicine, Government Medical College, Surat³Senior Resident, Department of Emergency Medicine, Government Medical College, Surat⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Government Medical College, Surat⁵Senior Consultant and Head, Department of GI Surgery, Aryavart Hospital, Meerut⁶Professor, Department of Physiology, Pacific Medical College & Hospital, Udaipur

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Abstract:**Background:** Hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning, particularly from yellow phosphorus, is a major public health concern, especially in developing countries. The role of coagulation abnormalities, such as activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) and international normalized ratio (INR), in predicting outcomes in these cases remains underexplored. This study aims to evaluate the prognostic significance of these bleeding profile parameters in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted at New Civil Hospital, Surat, India, from ethical clearance to May 2024. Seventy patients, aged 18 years or older, with a history of rodenticide poisoning and confirmed hepatotoxicity, were included. Patients were classified based on mortality and morbidity outcomes. Bleeding profile parameters, including aPTT and INR, were analyzed for their association with clinical outcomes.**Results:** Of the 70 patients, 11 (15.7%) died, and 59 (84.3%) recovered. A total of 38 (54.2%) required ICU admission due to severe illness. Elevated aPTT levels were significantly associated with morbidity, with 88% of severely ill patients showing elevated levels ($p < 0.00001$), while no significant association was found with mortality ($p = 0.51883$). Similarly, elevated INR levels were significantly correlated with morbidity (52.6% of severely ill patients, $p = 0.00012$), but not with mortality ($p = 0.18110$).**Conclusion:** While serum aPTT and INR levels are not reliable predictors of mortality in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning, they are significantly associated with morbidity, particularly the need for ICU admission. These parameters can assist in identifying patients at higher risk for severe illness but should be considered alongside other clinical indicators for comprehensive prognosis. Further studies with larger sample sizes and additional biomarkers are warranted to refine prognostic models.**Keywords:** Hepatotoxicity, Rodenticide Poisoning, Coagulation Profile, ICU Admission Risk, Prognostic Biomarkers, Liver Injury, Public Health ToxicologyThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Rodenticide poisoning, especially from substances like yellow phosphorus, is a growing health concern, particularly in developing countries like India, where it is a common cause of self-inflicted harm. Yellow phosphorus, which can cause severe hepatotoxicity and acute liver failure, accounts for around 30% of rodenticide-related fatalities (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2020). [1] Deliberate pesticide ingestion leads to over 500,000 cases annually, with rodenticide poisoning contributing significantly (Abhilash et al., 2022). [2] In India, regions like Tamil Nadu report a higher incidence, exacerbated by the widespread use of rodenticides in agriculture (Nalabothu et al., 2014). [3]

Rodenticides, including yellow phosphorus and aluminum phosphide, are highly toxic and often lead to high mortality rates, due to the lack of antidotes (Mishra et al., 2017). [4] While liver damage is well-known, the prognostic role of bleeding profile abnormalities—such as prolonged prothrombin time and low platelet count—remains underexplored. This study seeks to evaluate how coagulation parameters can predict outcomes in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning. [5,6]

Materials and Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at New Civil Hospital, Surat, a tertiary care center in South

Gujarat, from ethical clearance until May 2024. A convenient sampling method was used to recruit patients admitted to the Medicine Ward who met the inclusion criteria: adults aged 18 years or older with a history of rodenticide poisoning and willingness to participate. Exclusion criteria included patients with non-hepatotoxic rodenticides, those who ingested rodenticides mixed with other toxic substances, and individuals with pre-existing liver conditions such as acute or chronic hepatitis B/C. The study aimed to include 70-80 cases based on previous data from the Medicine Ward at NCHS, Surat, until the required sample size was reached. Data were collected using a predesigned, semi-structured performa, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment.

The study was approved by the hospital's ethical committee.

Results

This study assessed the relationship between bleeding profile parameters—specifically activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) and international normalized ratio (INR)—and clinical outcomes (mortality and morbidity) in patients with hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning. A total of 70 patients were included, with 11 (15.7%) deaths and 59 (84.3%) recoveries. The patients were categorized based on the severity of their condition, with 38 (54.2%) requiring ICU admission (severely ill) and 32 (45.8%) not requiring ICU admission.

Table 1: Association of Bleeding Profile with Mortality and Morbidity in Hepatotoxic Rodenticide Poisoning
Mortality and Bleeding Profile

Bleeding Profile	Mortality (n=70)	Morbidity (n=70)
Serum aPTT Levels		
Elevated	10 (23.8%)	37 (88%)
Normal	1 (3.5%)	1 (3.5%)
Total	11 (15.7%)	38 (54.2%)
p-value	0.51883	0.00001
Statistical Significance	Not Significant	Significant
INR Levels		
Elevated	8 (21.0%)	20 (52.6%)
Normal	3 (9.3%)	3 (9.3%)
Total	11 (15.7%)	23 (32.8%)
p-value	0.18110	0.00012
Statistical Significance	Not Significant	Significant

Serum aPTT Levels:

Elevated aPTT levels were observed in 10 patients (23.8%) who died and in 32 (76.2%) who recovered. Normal aPTT levels were seen in 1 (3.5%) patient who died, while 27 (96.5%) recovered. No significant association was found between aPTT and mortality ($\chi^2 = 3.7795$, $p = 0.51883$), indicating that aPTT is not a reliable predictor of mortality in rodenticide poisoning.

INR Levels:

Elevated INR levels were found in 8 patients (21.0%) who died, and in 30 (79.0%) who recovered. In the normal INR group, 3 patients (9.3%) died and 29 (90.7%) recovered. The chi-square analysis showed no significant association between elevated INR and mortality ($\chi^2 = 1.7885$, $p = 0.18110$), suggesting that INR alone does not significantly influence mortality outcomes.

Morbidity and Bleeding Profile

Serum aPTT Levels:

A significant association was found between elevated aPTT levels and severe illness (ICU admis-

sion). Elevated aPTT levels were found in 37 (88%) of the severely ill patients, compared to only 5 (12%) in the non-severely ill group. The chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 48.36$, $p = 0.00001$) revealed that elevated aPTT levels were strongly associated with the need for ICU admission.

INR Levels:

Elevated INR levels were found in 20 (52.6%) severely ill patients. The chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 14.73$, $p = 0.00012$) confirmed a significant association between elevated INR and the severity of illness (ICU admission).

Summary of Results

Analysis of aPTT and INR levels revealed significant associations with morbidity, with both elevated aPTT (88%) and INR (52.6%) strongly correlated with ICU admission. However, neither aPTT nor INR levels showed significant associations with mortality (p-values: 0.51883 and 0.18110). These results suggest that while these parameters are useful for assessing the severity of illness, they are not reliable predictors of mortality in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning. They can, however, guide

clinical management, particularly in determining ICU needs.

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the relationship between bleeding profile parameters—serum activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) and international normalized ratio (INR)—and clinical outcomes in patients with hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning. A total of 70 patients were included, of which 11 (15.7%) died and 59 (84.3%) recovered. Patients were categorized based on their need for intensive care, with 38 (54.2%) requiring ICU admission and 32 (45.8%) not. [7-12]

Serum aPTT and INR as Prognostic Indicators of Mortality

Our study found no significant association between aPTT and INR levels and mortality. Elevated aPTT was observed in 23.8% of patients who died, compared to 76.2% of those who recovered, while elevated INR was found in 21.0% of patients who died. Statistical analysis revealed p-values of 0.51883 and 0.18110, respectively, indicating that these bleeding profile parameters are not reliable predictors of mortality in rodenticide poisoning. [13-18]

This aligns with prior research that suggests while coagulation abnormalities are common in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning, they do not directly predict patient mortality (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2020; Nalabothu et al., 2014). [19] Rodenticide poisoning causes complex systemic effects, and factors beyond coagulation, such as the timing of medical intervention and multi-organ failure, play a larger role in determining patient outcomes.

Serum aPTT and INR as Prognostic Indicators of Morbidity [20]

In contrast to mortality, elevated aPTT and INR levels were significantly associated with morbidity, particularly the need for ICU admission. Elevated aPTT was observed in 88% of severely ill patients, while elevated INR was found in 52.6% of the same group. These findings suggest that aPTT and INR levels can be useful in assessing the severity of illness in rodenticide poisoning and determining the need for intensive care (Mishra et al., 2017; Govindarajan et al., 2021). [21,22]

Coagulation disturbances, including elevated aPTT and INR, reflect liver dysfunction, a key complication in rodenticide poisoning. The significant association with ICU admission underlines the role of coagulation abnormalities in predicting severe outcomes. These parameters can help clinicians identify patients at higher risk of complications and guide clinical decisions, such as the need for close monitoring and intensive care.

Limitations of Coagulation Parameters as Prognos-

tic Indicators

Despite the significant association with morbidity, aPTT and INR levels are not sufficient as sole prognostic tools. While these parameters provide valuable insight into the coagulation status, the complex nature of rodenticide poisoning means that other factors—such as the specific rodenticide type, dose, and underlying health conditions—likely play a more significant role in mortality (Sardar et al., 2019). [23]

Moreover, the small sample size of 70 patients limits the ability to detect subtle, clinically significant associations, suggesting that larger studies are needed to confirm these findings. These results also point to the multifactorial nature of mortality in rodenticide poisoning, where coagulation abnormalities may be secondary to other critical factors, including liver injury and organ failure (Gaddis, 1981). [24]

Clinical Implications

While aPTT and INR levels were not reliable predictors of mortality, they remain valuable for assessing the severity of illness and guiding decisions regarding ICU admission. Monitoring these parameters can help clinicians determine which patients are at higher risk of complications and require more intensive care. [25]

However, these markers should not be used in isolation. A more comprehensive approach, including liver function tests, clinical scoring systems, and other biomarkers, will likely provide more accurate prognostic information. This approach is essential for improving patient management and optimizing treatment decisions in rodenticide poisoning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, serum aPTT and INR levels were significantly associated with morbidity, particularly the need for ICU admission, but not with mortality in hepatotoxic rodenticide poisoning. These parameters can assist in identifying patients who require intensive care, but their predictive value for mortality remains limited. Further research with larger sample sizes and additional biomarkers is needed to refine prognostic models and enhance patient outcomes. A holistic clinical approach, integrating coagulation profiles and other clinical indicators, remains essential for improving the management of rodenticide poisoning.

Reference

1. Gopalakrishnan S, Kandasamy S, Iyyadurai R. Rodenticide poisoning: Critical appraisal of patients at a tertiary care center. *Indian J Crit Care Med.* 2020;24(5):295–8.
2. Abhilash KPP, Chandran J, Murugan S, Rabbi N AS, Selvan J, Jindal A, et al. Changing trends in the profile of rodenticide poisoning.

- Med J Armed Forces India [Internet]. 2022;78: S139–44.
3. Nalabothu M, Monigari N, Acharya R, Resident J. Clinical Profile and Outcomes of Rodenticide Poisoning in Tertiary Care Hospital. *Int J Sci Res Publ.* 2014;5(8):1–12.
 4. Sardar D, Mathews N, Mammen J, Nair SC, Jacob S, Patel L, et al. Rodenticidal hepatotoxicity: Raised plasma Von Willebrand factor levels predict in-hospital survival. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 2019;38(6):527–33.
 5. Mishra AK, Devakiruba NS, Jasmine S, Sathyendra S, Zachariah A, Iyadurai R. Clinical spectrum of yellow phosphorous poisoning in a tertiary care centre in South India: A case series. *Trop Doct.* 2017;47(3):245–9.
 6. Govindarajan R, Ramamoorthy G, Shanmugam RM, Bavanandam S, Murugesan M, Shanmugam C, et al. Rodenticide ingestion is an important cause of acute hepatotoxicity in Tamil Nadu, southern India. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 2021;40(4):373–9.
 7. Gummin DD, Mowry JB, Spyker DA, Brooks DE, Osterthaler M, Banner W, et al. 2017 Annual Report of the American Association of Poison Control Centers' National Poison Data System (NPDS). *Clin Toxicol.* 2018;3650.
 8. Lo R. White phosphorus poisoning by oral ingestion of firecrackers or little devils: Current experience in Ecuador. *Clin Toxicol.* 2011;29–33.
 9. Paul K, Abhilash P, Arul J, Jayakaran J. Rodenticide Poisoning: Literature Review and Management. *Curr Med Issue.* 2019;129–33.
 10. Tudi M, Ruan HD, Wang L, Lyu J, Sadler R, Connell D, et al. Agriculture Development, Pesticide Application and Its Impact on the Environment. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021; 18:1–23.
 11. Zhang Q, Xia Z, Wu M, Wang L. Human health risk assessment of DDTs and HCHs through dietary exposure in Nanjing, China. *Chemosphere.* 2017; 177:211–6.
 12. Barnhoorn IEJ, Bornman MS, Rensburg CJ Van, Bouwman H. DDT residues in water, sediment, and biota from a currently DDT-sprayed area. *Chemosphere.* 2009;77(9):1236–41.
 13. Karami-mohajeri S, Abdollahi M. Human & Experimental Toxicology. *Hum Exp Toxicol.* 2011; 30:1119–29.
 14. Horton MK, Barr DB, Louis ED. Prenatal Exposure to the Organophosphate Pesticide Chlorpyrifos and Childhood Tremor. *Neurotoxicology.* 2015; 03:159–84.
 15. Thongprakaisang S, Thiantanawat A, Rangkadilok N, Suriyo T, Satayavivad J. Glyphosate induces human breast cancer cells growth via estrogen receptors. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2013; 59:129–36.
 16. Samsel A, Seneff S. Glyphosate, pathways to modern diseases II: Celiac sprue and gluten intolerance. *Interdiscip Toxicol.* 2013;6(4):159–84.
 17. Feinstein DL, Akpa BS, Ayee MA, Boullerne AI, Brodsky SV, Gidalevitz D, et al. The emerging threat of superwarfarins: history, detection, mechanisms, and countermeasures. *Annu New York Acad Sci.* 2017;1374(1):111–22.
 18. Li Q, Kobayashi M, Kawada T. Carbamate Pesticide-Induced Apoptosis in Human T Lymphocytes. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2015;3633–45.
 19. Wogalter MS, State C, Carolina N, Jarrard SW, Academy USM, Point W, et al. Influence of Warning Label Signal Words on Perceived Hazard Level. *Hum Factors.* 1994;36(3):547–56.
 20. Isackson B, Irizarry L. Rodenticide Toxicity. In: National Library of Medicine, National Institutes of Health. 2023.
 21. Wang R, Zhuo L, Wang Y, Ren L, Liu Q, Liu L. Lessons learned from poisoning cases caused by 2 illegal rodenticides. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2016;41(September):4–7.
 22. Ravikanth R, Sandeep S, Philip B. Acute Yellow Phosphorus Poisoning Causing Fulminant Hepatic Failure with Parenchymal Hemorrhages and Contained Duodenal Perforation. *Indian J Crit Care Med.* 2017; 60:238–42.
 23. Tabor D, Tassew SF. Outcome of Rodenticide Poisoning and Its Associated Factors Among Adult Patients Admitted with Rodenticide Poisoning at the Emergency Unit of Debre Tabor Comprehensive Specialized. *Dove Press.* 2023; 189–97.
 24. Gaddis GP. Acute Yellow Phosphorus Poisoning from Pesticide Pastes. *Clin Toxicol.* 1981; 18(6):693–711.
 25. Krell WS, Shah AK, Schmidt CJ. Fatal Bromethalin Poisoning. *J Forensic Sci.* 2006;51(5): 1154–7.